

APPLICATION OF TACTICAL SATELLITE COMMUNICATIONS ON THE MODERN BATTLEFIELD

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the decision process which a Commander of a US Army Corps experiences as he allocates his tactical satellite assets in support of his Command, Control, and Communication (C3) system. The paper analyzes the C3 system utilized by VII (US) Corps in the execution of two phases of its General Defense Plan: transition to war and initial combat operations. The role played by tactical satellite (TACSAT) assets in these phases is discussed in detail.

The conclusion of this analysis is that tactical satellite equipment provides a reliable and flexible means of communication which plays a critical role in the overall C3 system of the Corps. The flexibility, reliability, and mobility of tactical satellite assets allows the Corps Commander to utilize TACSAT as a combat force multiplier, insuring that he is able to execute command and control over the entire length and breadth of the modern battlefield.

INTRODUCTION

The date is 29 September 1993; the time is 0743Z. Intelligence reports had been coming in for hours indicating that Soviet military activity had been increasing along the East/West German borders. General Harris, Supreme Allied Commander, was sitting in his large overstuffed chair in the SHAPE war headquarters briefing room. His staff had just completed giving him a complete situation briefing and had recommended that all allied forces be placed on alert status and be moved to wartime locations in response to the hostile Soviet threat. The General sat quietly for a minute and then turned toward his Chief of Operations. He silently nodded his head and approved his staff's recommendation.

Major Jim Johnson was operations officer on duty in the VII(US) Corps Emergency Operations Center at Kelly Barracks, Stuttgart West Germany. It had been a quiet tour of duty so far and he hoped that it would continue. Suddenly, the HOT LINE from Central Army Group (CENTAG) War Headquarters broke the days silence. "Another alert," was the thought that raced through Major Johnson's mind. But the instructions he received were not the start of another alert, but rather the first steps in preparation for war.

Colonel Gleason, Commander of the 93d Signal Brigade, sat at his desk as his operations officer

and deputy commander detailed the instructions which the brigade had received from VII Corps Headquarters: The brigade was to assemble its forces and begin its transition to war. This included establishing a tactical communications system within the Corps' area of operation, tying all of the Corps' major commands together as they moved from their garrison locations to their initial battle positions. Fortunately, thought COL Gleason, the brigade had practiced this plan regularly and had become very adept at establishing the required command and control communications (C3) overlay system called for in the Corps' transition to war plan. After hearing the current status of his units from his deputy commander, Colonel Gleason turned to his S-3 and instructed the brigade's "Crash Packages" to deploy immediately and establish the beginning of the Corps Communication System. These "Crash Packages" consist of tactical satellite (TACSAT) terminals and Mobile Subscriber Grid System access switches which deploy quickly to pre-designated wartime locations of each of VII Corps major commands and establish the initial command, control communications system.

Upon receiving their instructions, these "Crash Packages" deployed from several locations within the Corps area of operation and were in location and operating within hours of receiving their notification. As major commands of the Corps moved into their initial battle positions, they slipped underneath a tactical C3 umbrella which tied them directly to the Corps' war headquarters. This TACSAT communications network provided the critical links necessary to pass updated intelligence and operational instructions to the battle staffs of the Corps' fighting forces; insuring that the Corps Commander had positive command and control during these crucial first hours of preparation for battle.

This fictional description of the beginning of a NATO/Warsaw Pact confrontation is intended to highlight the importance of tactical communications during the initial hours of such a confrontation as forces are transitioning from their peacetime locations and activities to their wartime locations and postures. Tactical satellite communications will play a key role in this initial communication system as well as in the total tactical communication system established by the Corps during combat operations. The purpose of this paper is to discuss the role of tactical satellite communications in the Corps' overall communications architecture and to describe the

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decision process which the Corps Commander and his staff will experience as they allocate TACSAT assets as part of the total command, control communications system. The methodology we will use will be first to describe the TACSAT assets which are available to the Corps and discuss their role in the overall communications architecture. Then show how TACSAT could be used in two different tactical communications scenarios in modern warfare: transition from peace to war and initial combat operations. This discussion will allow us to draw some conclusions on the usefulness of tactical satellite communications on the modern battlefield.

TACTICAL SATELLITE ASSETS - A DESCRIPTION

In 1971, the US Army defined the requirement for a tactical satellite communications capability. The Army stated that a need existed for a multichannel communications means which was tactical, mobile, survivable, and independent of siting restriction encountered in terrestrial tactical communications systems. In response to this need, the Army began the development of the Tactical Satellite Multichannel Initial Communication System. This system consisted of two types of TACSAT terminals, the systems necessary to control TACSAT deployments and the equipment necessary to interface them with the Defense Communications System. Presently, the US Army is procuring and fielding TACSAT terminals to tactical communication units worldwide. These terminals will be located in units which provide communications to Theater, Corps and Division headquarters elements.

The AN/TSC-85A is a tactical satellite earth terminal capable of transmitting and receiving up to 96 channels (48 channels via internal multiplex equipment) of voice and data via a SHF carrier. The AN/TSC-85A is capable of nodal, non-nodal, or point-to-point operations in tactical switching networks. The nodal capability refers to the employment of one terminal serving as a nodal or hub station, simultaneously providing full duplex multichannel links to as many as four widely dispersed destinations using the same satellite. Limited equipment redundancy is provided within the AN/TSC-85A, in the RF, modem, and Tactical Signal Processor (TSSP) sections. The terminal is mounted on two standard 2½ ton tactical vehicles with one carrying the S-280 shelter containing the terminal components and the other transporting the antenna. Each vehicle tows a standard 15 KW diesel power unit.

The AN/TSC-93A is also a tactical satellite earth terminal which is capable of transmitting and receiving up to 24 channels of voice and data using self-contained multiplex equipment. The AN/TSC-93A terminal is used as a non-nodal or point-to-point terminal in tactical switching networks. The terminal is mounted on two standard 1¼ tactical vehicles with one carrying the S-250 shelter containing the terminal components and the other transporting the antenna. Each vehicle tows a 10 KW diesel power unit.

These earth terminals are designed to work in a hub/spoke arrangement where the AN/TSC-85A is the hub and the AN/TSC-93A acts as the spoke. In this arrangement (shown in Figure 1), the AN/TSC-85A is able to communicate with up to four

FIGURE 1

AN/TSC-93A terminals. The TACSAT terminals will provide the transmission means for interconnecting switching assemblages in the Mobile Subscriber Grid System (MSGS) found in the US Army's Corps and Divisions and within the TRI-TAC switching network found at Echelons Above Corps. Within the MSGS architecture, TACSAT has four possible roles:

- (1) Connect access switches at key headquarters,
- (2) Connect an access switch to a node central,
- (3) Connect two node centrals,
- and, (4) Connect a MSGS node central to the switching network found at Echelons Above Corps.

At Echelons Above Corps or Theater Level, TACSAT terminals will provide a transmission means for connecting TRI-TAC circuit and message switches located at area communication nodes and key headquarters.

As mentioned earlier, TACSAT terminals will be assigned to signal units at Theater, Corps, and Division levels. A representation of their deployment on the battlefield is shown in Figure 2. This diagram represents a Theater slice of the battlefield depicting the typical connectivity which would exist from theater through division level. However, actual connectivity will be dictated by the communication needs of the commander at a particular place and time on the battlefield.

TACTICAL SATELLITE COMMUNICATIONS - ITS USE IN WARTIME

The use of TACSAT on the modern battlefield will be a function of several factors: Mission, Enemy Situation, Terrain, Troops and Time. As the Corps commander and his staff plan the course of the battle and design a command, control, and communication system to support that battle, each of these factors must be taken into consideration. The use of TACSAT on the battlefield will become clearer if we analyze two possible situations encountered on the battlefield and show how TACSAT

FIGURE 2

supports the C3 system within these two scenarios. The first scenario will be the use of TACSAT during the initial phase of a European war; the transition from a peacetime posture to full preparation for war. The second will be the use of TACSAT in a fully activated communications network during combat operations.

The backdrop for both of these scenarios will be the US Army's forward deployed VII Corps. This Corps, headquartered in Stuttgart, West Germany, is a subordinate unit to NATO's Central Army Group (CENTAG) with the mission of defending a large portion of West Germany's frontier along the East German and Czechoslovakia border. The Corps forward deployed forces includes two US divisions, a NATO division, a US Armored Cavalry Regiment and Forward Station, as well as a full corps support command, signal, engineer, military intelligence and military police brigades. The VII (US) Corps is a complete fighting force responsible for the defense of a large part of Northern Bavaria. A representation of the corps deployment in West Germany is shown in Figure 3. This deployment is

FIGURE 3

spread over a variety of terrain including several mountainous areas, large open valleys, and is criss-crossed by several major water and urban obstacles.

The command and control problems of the Corps are staggering. The Signal Brigade assigned to

the Corps has the mission of installing, operating, and maintaining the communication system used by the Corps commander to exercise command and control over his forces. This brigade has a variety of assets at its disposal in order to install this C3 system. They include terrestrial and tactical satellite multichannel radio equipment, switching equipment, radio access equipment, mobile and stationary subscriber terminals. In addition to the mobile subscriber grid system, a variety of single channel radio nets are operated on the battlefield utilizing both the VHF Single Channel Ground Airborne Radio System and the Improved HF Radio. The signal brigade establishes a grid network within the Corps area of operation utilizing terrestrial multichannel radios and nodal switching equipment. The Signal Brigade then extends access to this grid network by the use of terrestrial multichannel and unit switchboards a key command posts on the battlefield. Once fully established, this grid network becomes very flexible and survivable; able to be adjusted to and accommodate the flow of the battle and needs of the commander.

During the first scenario we will discuss, the Corps' transition from peace to war, tactical satellite will provide the backbone transmission system interconnecting the tactical command posts of the corps fighting forces as they move from garrison headquarters to their initial battle positions. During this transition period, the Corps and its subordinate commands are involved to several activities: Combat upload of all equipment, distribution of the basic load of ammunition and war supplies, movement to the area of combat operations and closeout of military community facilities. The Corps Signal Brigade is involved in the same activities. As the brigade moves into the corps area of operation, it begins to establish the grid network and tying together nodes established by the division signal elements. The final result is a complete mobile subscriber grid system which is poised to meet and satisfy the C3 requirements of the corps.

However, this grid network takes time to establish. The complete network will not be established until all elements of the corps are deployed. Starting from the initial notification, the Corps Commander and his staff must have

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positive command and control over his forces as they move from garrison to field locations. Tactical satellite communications appears to be the most efficient way to provide this connectivity. The "Crash Packages" described in the opening of this paper provide the ideal package to install a skeleton C3 network during these initial hours of transition. The "Crash Package" consists of tactical satellite earth terminals and a mobile subscriber grid system access switch. Upon order, these packages deploy to predesignated locations in the corps area of operation and establish a limited switching network. A representation of this network is shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4

As combat units deploy from garrison to initial battle positions, they link up with the TACSAT terminals and access switches which are already in place and operation tactical CP's are then tied into this limited tactical switching network which links them to the VII (US) Corps war headquarters for an immediate update of intelligence data and the operational situation. Connectivity is expanded as the entire MSGS is established.

Therefore as the Corps Commander and his staff analyze this portion of the battle plan the following analysis evolves:

Mission: During transition from peace to war, the Corps Commander must have positive command and control over his combat forces. Therefore, the Signal Brigade must establish a limited C3 system during this crucial period.

Enemy: Enemy forces are massing on the international border but hostilities have not begun. Terrorist and sabotage activity is possible.

Terrain: This limited communication system must interconnect all major tactical headquarters which are spread throughout the corps area. A tactical terrestrial communication system does not exist at this point in time to provide this connectivity.

Time: This communication system must be established and operational within a few hours of notification.

Troops: Minimal communication assets are available this early in the transition period. Also, the communication system must be quickly installed and be totally operational within a few hours of notification.

Based on this analysis, the use of tactical satellite communications to satisfy the need for a quickly installed C3 network is the most reasonable approach. It will provide the Corps Commander with a reliable, flexible communication means which meets his command and control requirements at this time in the conflict.

As the Corps completes its transition from peace to war, combat forces take their place on the battlefield. Combat support troops establish themselves in tactical configurations and prepare themselves to sustain the battle. Combat Service Support units establish the wartime supply network which gets bullets and food from the rear area to the front. The Signal Brigade establishes, along with the division signal battalions, the mobile subscriber grid network. Node centrals are established; access is provided to fixed and mobile subscribers. All the combat power of the corps is poised and ready to respond to any situation.

As combat operations begin, tactical satellite terminals will again play a key role in the Corps tactical C3 system. As mentioned earlier, tactical satellite has four possible uses in MSGS: connect access switches, connect an access switch to a node central, interconnect two node centrals, and provide the transmission connection between a MSGS node central and the switching network found at Echelons Above Corps. As the Corps' combat forces become engaged in battle, it is going to be necessary to adjust the grid network to meet the communication needs of the commander. Tactical satellite will be an important asset during these transitions.

A scenario which exhibits this use of TACSAT would involve a possible counterattack by one of the Corps' divisions. As the initial battle progresses, the enemy forces are able to push back the forward defensive line of the Corps Divisions. However, because of differences in defensive terrain, the enemy exposes one flank as it moves into the Corps Main battle area. The Corps Commander decides to execute a counterattack plan which takes advantage of the enemy's exposed flank. In order to execute this plan, one division must shift its forces prior to the execution of the attack. This shift requires that the node centrals and access switches servicing that division must be moved in order to accommodate the shifts in forces. During this move, it is determined that the Division Tactical Operations Center (DTAC) will move forward to better control the counter-attack. The Corps Commander must have continuous communications with this headquarters during the attack. His staff recommends the use of tactical satellite communication in order to maintain

communication with the DTAC while the division communication assets adjust to their new mission. Therefore, a tactical satellite terminal from the Corps Signal Brigade to be dispatched to the DTAC's new location. It is linked with one of the Corps' Node Centrals and switchboard circuits are terminated on the DTAC's access switch. The use of this TACSAT link insures that positive command and control will be maintained between the Corps Commander and the Division's battle staff during the execution of the counterattack.

The analysis done by the Corps Commander's staff in order to determine how best to command and control the division during this planned counterattack results in the selection of tactical satellite equipment as the means to provide the needed connectivity. The methodology the staff follows in their analysis is:

Mission: Maintain positive command and control over the division executing the counter-attack.

Enemy: The enemy is attacking across the international border and is placing heavy pressure on defending forces. However, because of difference in terrain he exposed one flank as he attacks forward.

Terrain: The DTAC controlling the counter-attack must move in order to better control the combat forces during the attack. The divisions communications system must be adjusted to meet the communication needs generated by the new tactical mission.

Time: The counterattack must be accomplished quickly in order to take advantage of the enemy's exposed flank.

Troops: As the DTAC shifts its position to better control its combat forces during the counterattack, the divisions communication system will also be shifted to meet changing communications requirements of the division's forces. A communication link must be maintained between Corps battle staff and DTAC controlling the counterattack.

Based on this analysis, the use of tactical satellite is best means to provide the link between the Corps headquarters and the DTAC. The access switch located at the DTAC is tied directly to a node central installed by the Corps Signal Brigade. This TACSAT link provides the Corps Commander with a means necessary to exercise positive command and control over his fighting forces during the execution of the counterattack.

TACTICAL SATELLITE COMMUNICATIONS - A CONCLUSION

These two scenarios illustrate the usefulness of tactical satellite communications on the modern battlefield. TACSAT gives the commander a flexible, reliable communication asset which has several uses within the command, control, communications system. This asset, with its mobility, reliability, and flexibility, becomes a combat force multiplier to the Corps Commander,

greatly increasing his command and control capabilities with the use of a limited, but powerful, asset - tactical satellite communications.